

ISSN : 0973-7057

Assessment of nutrient quality status by interrelationship between Physical traits macronutrients of agricultural land in Baliapur, Dhanbad, Jharkhand

Sonam Bharti^{a*}, Lal Bihari Singh^b & Adarsh Kumar Srivastava^c

^aUniversity Department Environmental Science and Disaster Management, BBMK University, Dhanbad, Jharkhand, India

^bUniversity Department of Zoology, BBMK University, Dhanbad, Jharkhand, India

^cKrishi Vigyan Kendra Bokaro, Jharkhand, India

Received : 04th January, 2024 ; Revised : 31st January, 2024

DOI:-<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14292008>

Abstract- To analyse physical and macronutrient factors of agricultural soil to help farmers determine crops for better yield. Mrida Parikshak conducted the analysis of the soil sample, organic carbon estimated by Walkley and Black organic carbon method. The recorded mean soil pH 5.66 indicates acidic nature. The average organic carbon content 0.2734% falls within low range on soil fertility standards. The average value of available Nitrogen is 118 kg/ha⁻¹, Phosphorus 17.260 kg ha⁻¹, Potassium 117.63 kg ha⁻¹ and Sulphur 51.62 mg/kg. Corn, oats, barley, and potatoes favour pH ranges between 5.5 and 6.5. Relatively low organic carbon content suggests a potential need for organic matter amendments to improve crop fertility and long-term sustainability. Positive relationship implies that higher organic carbon levels enhance nitrogen availability, supporting plant growth and productivity. Positive correlation of available sulphur with nitrogen and potassium indicates potential synergistic effects or co-occurrence of these nutrients, for beneficial crop nutrient uptake and soil fertility management. Available phosphorus and potassium show negative relationship implying competitive interactions making nutrient management crucial to optimize crop yield potential, avoiding deficiencies. Negative correlation between available phosphorus and sulphur suggests potential antagonistic effects that may influence nutrient availability for plant uptake.

Key words: Crop selection, Macronutrient, Nutrient analysis, Physical properties and Their co-relationship

INTRODUCTION

In order to keep trophic levels in terrestrial ecosystems stable, the pedosphere is responsible for maintaining production. The significance of biotic and abiotic components in ecosystems is used to examine the role that abiotic resources or components (soil), play in maintaining the biotic component (plants) and how the organic matter, mineral matter, air and water that make up soil, contribute

to the survival of producers and microorganisms. Three fundamental criteria are used to classify the nutrients in the soil, including Physical and Chemical attributes respectively like how the potential hydrogen ion concentration defines pH. The term pH refers to the concentration of basic and acid ions in soil. Plants in soil with low pH levels will not flourish, and many minerals will not breakdown and reach the plant.¹ The pH of the soil affects the process of bioavailability, nutrient absorption, and microbial activity.² The bulk of

*Corresponding author :

Phone : 7004307268

E-mail : lalbiharis938@gmail.com

micronutrients (B, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, and Zn) are more accessible within a pH range of 5 to 7, whereas macronutrients (N, K, Ca, Mg, and S) are more available within a pH range of 6.5 to 8.³ There are four primary activities that soil microorganisms carry out in the cycling of organic matter in the soil.

The breakdown of organic wastes, the mineralization of nutrients, the movement of nutrients and organic carbon from one SOM pool to another, and the continuous release of carbon dioxide (CO₂) via microbial respiration and chemical oxidation are the first four processes.⁴ On the other hand, the number of non-specific ions present in the soil is indicated by electrical conductivity. It shows salinity, nutrients, and the ability to exchange ions. Non-specific ion concentration in the soil is indicated by waterflow, soil texture, bulk density, organic matter, organic carbon, and conductivity. It shows salinity, nutrients, and the ability to exchange ions. soil structure, bulk density, organic carbon, organic matter, water movement and its effect chemical properties of soil.^{5,6} Macronutrients, such as available nitrogen. The lithosphere, atmosphere, hydrosphere, and biosphere are all rich in nitrogen (N). Unlike potassium (K) and phosphorus (P), the other two key plant nutrients, rock deposits of nitrogen (N) in the lithosphere do not exist, thus air dinitrogen (N₂), which is unreactive, is converted to reactive forms of N to make fertiliser N. It is remarkable how little of this N-roughly in the first metre of the earth's crust-is found in the soil, primarily in biological forms. Typically, surface mineral soils have a total N concentration of 0.05 to 0.2 percent.⁷ Another crucial function is that they serve as constraints for plants and because pH affects how well plants absorb nitrogen.^{8,9} Second most essential nutrient is phosphorus it helps to develop growth of plant, healthy growth flower and vegetable. In soil phosphorus occur as orthophosphate and polyphosphate which are use in development of DNA and RNA respectively. Mycorrhiza fungi help to fixed Phosphate enzyme respectively.^{10,11} Soil contains potassium in the form of the K⁺ ion. The seventh most prevalent element in the crust of the planet, with an average concentration of 2.6%. Potassium is transported to the root via the soil's surface and subsurface layer, where it facilitates the growth of plant roots, improves grain production, and is required for seed formation.¹² The secondary macronutrient is sulphur, important for growth and development.¹³

Young leaves with interveinal chlorosis (green veins with yellow spaces in between) are affected by a manganese shortage. It is affected by low moisture content, high pH (greater than 6.5), and organic matter in the soil.¹⁴

Study Area

The research region is the Dhanbad district in the state of Jharkhand, which is located between 23°37'30"N-24°56'N latitude and 86°8'23"E-86°50'18"E longitude, as seen in Figure 1. Baghmara, Baliapur, Dhanbad, Govindpur, Jharia, Nirsa, Topchanchi, and Tundi are the eight blocks that make up the Dhanbad district. The region is covered in the Survey of India (1:50,000 scale) topsheet numbers 73 I/1, 73. I/2, 73 I/5, 73 I/6, 73 I/7, 73 I/9, 73 I/10, 73 I/13, and 73 I/14. The Barakar River surrounds the district, northern boundary, while the Damodar River forms its southern boundary. It is on these rivers that two significant reservoirs-Maithon and Panchet-are situated. Soil Samples were collected from Pilani Village of Baliapur region Dhanbad Five samples were collected from different sampling location at depth of 15 to 20 cm.¹⁵

Fig 1: Shows sample area (Baliapur)

METHOD & METHODOLOGY

Mrida Parikshak conducted the analysis of the soil sample. And organic carbon estimated by Walkley and Black organic carbon method.^{16,17}

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Table 1- Shows the Minimum and Maximum Range of soil Parameters

S.No	Parameter	Min.	Max.
1.	pH	5.51	6.12
2.	Organic carbon (%)	0.231	0.290
3.	Available Nitrogen (kg/ha ⁻¹)	110.2	122.96
4.	Available Phosphorus (kg/ha ⁻¹)	14.59	20.94
5.	Potassium (kg/ha ⁻¹)	86.52	92.12
6.	Sulphur (mg/kg)	37.22	66.29

Table 2- Shows the standard range of soil parameters.¹⁸

S. No.	Parameter	Low	Medium	High
1.	O.C (%)	<0.5	0.5-0.75	>0.75
2.	Available Nitrogen (kg/ha)	<280	280-560	>560
3.	Available Phosphorus (kg/ha)	<12.5	12.5-25	>25
4.	Available Potassium (kg/ha)	<135	135-335	>335
5.	Available Sulphur (kg/ha)	<10	10-20	>20

Table 3- Shows the relationship between various parameters

	OC	AN	AP	AK	AS
pH	-0.9972	0.79054	0.7905	0.9775	0.7249
OC	1	0.8649	-0.7812	-0.9795	0.7280
AN	-----	1	0.9130	0.6886	0.9247
AP	-----	-----	1	0.7589	-0.9753
K	-----	-----	-----	1	0.6081

Table 4- Shows the regression equation between various parameter

S.NO	Regression equation
1.	OC=-0.0925 pH + 0.7971
2.	AN=17.7328 pH + 219.0771
3.	AP= 9.1651 pH + 34.6867
4.	AK = 8.8628 pH + 37.8129
5.	AS= 36.7192 pH +156.2621
6.	AN= 191.8958 OC + 65.1737
7.	AP =-97.5326 OC + 9.4594
8.	AK =-95.6297 OC + 90.05
9.	AS = 354.4102 OC + 46.4537
10.	AP= 0.5137 AN + 43.2246
11.	AK = 0.3029 AN + 52.3615
12.	AS = 2.2730 AN -215.7491
13.	AK = 0.5646 AP + 78.4795
14.	AS= -0.2232 AP - 5.6796
15.	AS= 3.3972 AK -247.2912

Graph 1: Shows Co- relationship between pH and OC

Graph 2: Shows co-relationship between pH and Available Nitrogen

Graph 3: Shows co-relationship between pH and Available Phosphorus

Graph 4: Shows co-relationship between pH and Available Potassium

Graph 5: Shows co-relationship between pH and Available Sulphur

Graph 6: Shows co-relationship between Organic Carbon and Available Nitrogen

Graph 10: Shows co-relationship between Available Nitrogen and Available Phosphorous

Graph 7: Shows co-relationship between Organic Carbon and Available Phosphorous

Graph 12: Shows co-relationship between Available Nitrogen and Available Potassium

Graph 8: Shows co-relationship between Organic Carbon and Available Potassium

Graph 13: Shows co-relationship between Available Nitrogen and Available Sulphur

Graph 9: Shows co-relationship between Organic Carbon and Available Sulphur

Graph 14: Shows co-relationship between Available Phosphorous and Available Potassium

Bharti et al.- Assessment of nutrient quality status by interrelationship between Physical traits macronutrients of agricultural land in Baliapur, Dhanbad, Jharkhand

Graph 15: Shows co-relationship between Available Phosphorous and Available Sulphur

Graph 16: Shows co-relationship between Available Potassium and Available Sulphur

The study revealed a low concentration level of available nitrogen, organic carbon, and potassium. The medium range of available phosphorous and available sulphur are high. The pH value of the soil sample is acidic in nature. By adding lime, it makes it a favourable condition for the cultivation of crops.¹⁹ Urea is added to boost the available nitrogen content in the soil. The mean pH is 5.66, which is suitable for the cultivation of corn, oats, barely, and potatoes.⁴ There is a significant negative co-relationship between soil pH and organic carbon.¹⁹⁻²¹ And have a significant positive relationship with available nitrogen, available phosphorus²², available potassium, and available sulphur.^{23,24} The organic carbon mean value of 0.2734, which is low as per the standard range, can be improved by the addition of gypsum²⁵, because adding gypsum to soil reduces erosion by increasing the ability of the soil to soak up water after precipitation, thus reducing runoff. There is a significant positive relationship between soil organic carbon and available nitrogen and available sulphur²⁶ and a negative relationship between available phosphorus and available potassium. There is a significant positive relationship between available nitrogen, available phosphorus, available potassium, and available sulphur. There is a significant positive

relationship between available phosphorus and available potassium. There is a significant negative relationship between available phosphorus and available sulphur. There is positive relationship between available potassium and available sulphur.²³

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The study endeavour is warmly acknowledged by the authors for the lab support provided by Krishi Vigyan Kendra Baliapur of the Indian Council of Agricultural study (ICAR), Ranchi. I also thank the Principal of High School Dhanbad, Rajesh Kumar, for his assistance with soil sample and static analysis. The research project could not be finished without his assistance.

AUTHORSHIP & CONTRIBUTORSHIP

Initial conceptualization idea or research hypothesis given by Dr. Lal Bihari Singh, the laboratory, and the methodology of the data guided by Dr. Adarsh Kumar Srivastava. Analysis of data, graph, and write-up prepared by Sonam Bharti.

FUNDING SOURCE

Funding organisations from the commercial, nonprofit, and public sectors did not award grants for this study.

REFERENCE

1. **Thomas G. W. 1996.** Soil pH and soil acidity. *Methods of soil analysis: part 3 chemical methods*, **5**: 475-490.
2. **Neina D. 2019.** The role of soil pH in plant nutrition and soil remediation. *Applied and environmental soil science*. **2019**: 1-9.
3. **Reid R. J. 2001.** Mechanisms of micronutrient uptake in plants. *Functional Plant Biology*, **28(7)**: 661-668.
4. **McCauley A., Jones C., & Jacobsen J. 2009.** Soil pH and organic matter. *Nutrient management module*, **8(2)**: 1-12.
5. **Othaman N. N., Isa M. N., Ismail R. C., Ahmad M. I., & Hui C. K. 2020.** Factors that affect soil electrical conductivity (EC) based system for smart farming application. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2203, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
6. **Lund E. D. 2008.** Soil electrical conductivity. *Soil Science Step by Step Field Analysis*, 137-146.

7. Hofman G., & Van Cleemput O. 2004. Soil and plant nitrogen.
8. Walley F., Yates T., van Groenigen J. W., & van Kessel C. 2002. Relationships between soil nitrogen availability indices, yield, and nitrogen accumulation of wheat. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, **66(5)**: 1549-1561.
9. Penn C. J., & Camberato J. J. 2019. A critical review on soil chemical processes that control how soil pH affects phosphorus availability to plants. *Agriculture*, **9(6)**: 120.
10. Stutter M. I., Shand C. A., George T. S., Blackwell M. S., Bol R., MacKay R. L., ... & Haygarth P. M. 2012. Recovering phosphorus from soil: a root solution.
11. Turner B. L. 2008. Resource partitioning for soil phosphorus: a hypothesis. *Journal of Ecology*, **96(4)**: 698-702.
12. Sparks D. L., & Huang P. M. 1985. Physical chemistry of soil potassium. *Potassium in agriculture*, 201-276.
13. Bowker M. A., Belnap J., Davidson D. W., & Phillips S. L. 2005. Evidence for micronutrient limitation of biological soil crusts: importance to arid lands restoration. *Ecological Applications*, **15(6)**:1941-1951.
14. Chandra S., Singh P. K., Tiwari A. K., Panigrahy B. P. & Kumar A. 2015. Evaluation of hydrogeological factors and their relationship with seasonal water table fluctuation in Dhanbad district, Jharkhand, India. *ISH Journal of Hydraulic Engineering*, **21(2)**: 193-206.
15. Bhartey P. K., Singh Y. V., Sukirtee P. S., Kumar M., & Rai A. K. 2017. Available Macro Nutrient Status and their Relationship with Soil Physico-Chemical Properties of Mirzapur District of Uttar-Pradesh, India. *Int. J. Curr. Microbio. App. Sci*, **6(7)**: 2829-2837.
16. Bharti S., & Srivastava A. K. 2023. The co-relationship between iron and zinc and their importance as micronutrients in the agricultural land of Baliapur region, Dhanbad, Jharkhand.
17. Jamal A., Moon Y. S., & Zainul Abidin M. 2010. Sulphur-a general overview and interaction with nitrogen. *Australian J. of Crop Science*, **4(7)**: 523-529
18. Verma B. C., Datta S. P., Rattan R. K., & Singh A. K. 2010. Monitoring changes in soil organic carbon pools, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur under different agricultural management practices in the tropics. *Environ. monitoring and assessment*, **171**: 579-593.
19. Kemmitt S. J., Wright D., Goulding K. W., & Jones D. L. 2006. pH regulation of carbon and nitrogen dynamics in two agricultural soils. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, **38(5)**: 898-911.
20. Xu H. & Zhang C. 2021. Investigating spatially varying relationships between total organic carbon contents and pH values in European agricultural soil using geographically weighted regression. *Science of The Total Environment*, **752**: 141-977.
21. Sun X. L., Minasny B., Wu Y. J., Wang H. L., Fan X. H. & Zhang G. L. 2023. Soil organic carbon content increase in the east and south of China is accompanied by soil acidification. *Science of The Total Environment*, **857**: 159-253.
22. Pandey S. P., Singh R. S., & Mishra S. K. 2000. Availability of phosphorus and sulphur in Inceptisols of central Uttar Pradesh. *Journal of the Indian Society of Soil Science*, **48(1)**: 118-121.
23. Isitekhale H. H. E., Aboh S. I., & Oseghale E. S. 2013. Sulphur status of some soils in Edo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, **2(6)**: 91-95.
24. Srinivasarao C., Ganeshamurthy A. N., Ali M., Singh R. N., & Singh K. K. 2004. Sulphur fractions, distribution, and their relationships with soil properties in different soil types of major pulse-growing regions of India. *Communications in soil science and plant analysis*, **35(19-20)**: 2757-2769.
25. Basak N., Sheoran P., Sharma R., Yadav R. K., Singh R. K., Kumar S., ... & Sharma P. C. 2021. Gypsum and pressmud amelioration improve soil organic carbon storage and stability in sodic agroecosystems. *Land Degradation & Development*, **32(15)**: 4430-4444.
26. Singh R. P., & Mishra S. K. 2012. Available macro nutrients (N, P, K and S) in the soils of Chiraigaon block of district Varanasi (UP) in relation to soil characteristics. *Indian Journal of Scientific Research*, **3(1)**: 97-100.